

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AS A CATALYST FOR EFFECTIVE RISK MANAGEMENT IN THE FINANCIAL SECTOR: PERSPECTIVES, TOOLS AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract

The paper analyzes the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in risk management in the financial sector, with a special focus on software tools, challenges, and application perspectives. Through a multifaceted study based on available sources, as well as a review of relevant literature, the process of how artificial intelligence systems convert the process of identifying, analyzing, and controlling risks in the financial sector is discussed. By reviewing application systems based on artificial intelligence in the financial sector, i.e. their elementary benefits in the field of risk control, the paper points to advantages such as improved accuracy and efficiency, but also to challenges such as model transparency and regulatory and ethical compliance. Given the intensive development of technology and the growing value of the frequency of information flow, it is obvious that in the years ahead we will face the challenge of managerial affirmation towards modern systems based on artificial intelligence.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence Systems, Financial Sector, Risk Management

VEŠTAČKA INTELIGENCIJA KAO KATALIZATOR ZA EFIKASNO UPRAVLJANJE RIZICIMA U FINANSIJSKOM SEKTORU: PERSPEKTIVE, ALATI I IZAZOVI

Apstrakt

Rad analizira ulogu veštačke inteligencije u upravljanju rizicima u sektoru finansija, sa posebnim osvrtom na softverske alate, izazove i perspektive primene. Putem multiagaone studije zasnovane na dostupnim izvorima, kao i pregledu relevantne literature, razmatra se kako sistemi veštačke inteligencije sprovode proces identifikacije, analize i kontrole rizika u sektoru finansija. Pregledom primenljivih sistema zadnovanih na veštačkoj inteligenciji u sektoru finansija, odnosno njihovih elementarnih koristi u sferi kontrole rizika, u radu se ukazuje na prednosti kao što su poboljšana tačnost i efikasnost, ali i na izazove kao što su transparentnost modela i usklađenost propisa i etike. Imajući u vidu intenzivan razvoj tehnologije i rast učestalosti protoka informacija, očigledno je da ćemo se u godinama koje su pred nama suočiti sa izazovom menadžerske afirmacije prema savremenim sistemima zasnovanim na veštačkoj inteligenciji.

Gljučne reči: sistemi veštačke inteligencije, finansijski subjekti, upravljanje rizicima

INTRODUCTION

Today, following modern trends, the business environment and the way businesses are conducted are changing rapidly. Accordingly, the flexibility of business operations and the application of new models, methods, and tools to maintain and improve business operations are placed in the first place. This, of course, also applies to financial institutions. Customization to economic and financial changes and a dynamic environment, and effectively managing risks in the financial sector, reflect the basis for the stability and long-term survival of subjects in the financial sector. The successful application of innovative information technologies, supported by modern hardware and software solutions, and in particular the application of artificial intelligence, has enabled the improvement of the process of collection, metrics, analysis, information generation, and risk control, and improvement of management. In modern business conditions, financial institutions, such as banks, insurance companies, and investment funds, operate in a changing environment of pronounced uncertainty, a high level of digitalization, and regulatory mechanisms.

Artificial intelligence's capacity in risk management is seen as a distinct novelty and phase of the sector's digital transformation, with the potential to improve efficiency, accuracy, and speed of decision-making. Primarily, in the form of desk research, existing software solutions based on artificial intelligence are analyzed and used, and how they influence risk management processes, as well as their potential and limitations. In this regard, the paper aims to offer an analytical and synthetic overview of the role of artificial intelligence in financial risk management, relying exclusively

on available sources and successfully applied models, as well as an analysis of existing solutions.

Theoretical scope of risk management

In the first place, overtake refers to understanding the term of risk, and its further adjustment in the sector of finance. Risk implies the output of probability and the consequences of a certain undesirable, mostly unpredictable event or events. In the field of economics and finance, risk takes its own place and understanding. It refers to management decisions, before, during, and after the decision is made. Nevertheless, even in the case that the respective decision is not applied, the risk exists. From the perspective of economics and decision-making operations in management, risk management implies a protocol-systematic process of identifying, collecting, analyzing, measuring, evaluating, and controlling risks to minimize possible damages (ISO, 2018). The protocol above reflects the basis of economic and financial stability and is one of the most important elements of corporate governance (Jorion, 2007). Also, risks in this regard cover the timing. In case the decision is not made just in time, risks of undesirable events could occur.

Therefore, inside the field of finance, a long list of risk types figures, and their behavior fluctuates in terms of variables that depend on many factors. Thus, theory and practice determine the parameters of risks. Credit, market, operational, liquidity, legal, and regulatory types of risks are identified as the most important. Analysis and assessment of these parameters could take qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods. The strategic aim is to keep the risk of interest at the lowest level under the available resources. This approach takes a forecasting manner.

Heritage remains that risk assessment and further forecasting as a form of the risk assessment output, and its ranking are supported by a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods. Some of the most frequently applied methods are scenario analysis, the application of the risk consequences forecast and probability, and consequence matrices of risk occurrence. Further, except for these methods, the application of statistical tools such as regression models or Monte Carlo models for simulations plays a crucial role in risk assessment too.

However, the processes of globalization and new informational technologies innovations had a huge and radical impact on integrations in many spheres, including finance. These well-known innovations and integrations generated standards in the business sphere, but new sorts of communication channels, new financial products, new and more complex scope of competition. The frequency of communication, number of participants, and interactions among different and connected services have increased to a new level. The complexity increased. With the increasing complexity of the financial system, the high new dynamism of interactions on the market, and the amount of available data, the applied tools reflect the limitations in speed, adaptability, and accuracy (Power, 2009). Following these essential changes, recent and updated approaches to risk assessment and risk management issues are

conceptualized on the standards covered by ISO 31000. ISO 31000 provides, promotes, and insists on an integrated, systemic, and contextual understanding of risk in organizations, bearing in mind that all organizations are connected and depend on many factors.

Therefore, the business environment in the last decades has changed, and in this regard, the risk management approach has depended on humans. But in line with innovations, informational systems were improved. Namely, up to the end of the second decade of 21st century, or rather, traditional risk management and decision-making protocols in the sector of finance were largely dependent on human judgment and manual tools, but with the development of information technology systems, there has been a rapid development of applied hardware, software, internet-based networks, and algorithms, i.e. information systems. Aligning with this, the focus has increasingly shifted towards the basic applications of artificial intelligence systems and algorithms in this domain, but these platforms have been improved, updated and upgraded continuously up to today. The beneficial potential of artificial intelligence systems in the protocols of identification and assessment of financial risks has been increasingly and sophisticated determined.

Today, the full capacities of the benefits that this new flexible smart informational system brings with it have not been fully defined. Its capacity is still not well and precisely rounded. Even though this innovative use is relatively new and has not yet been established and accepted in its full capacity as a helpful tool in business operations, financial sector experts and managers understand that it enables effective and efficient and automated processing of large data sets and the identification of hidden patterns that are not accessible to classical statistical techniques (Russell & Norvig, 2020). Additionally, a full capacity application of machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) provides the opportunity to update and innovate certain models that can be independently upgraded over time. Thus, achieving greater flexibility and robustness in responding to dynamic financial conditions (Goodfellow, Bengio, & Courville, 2016).

Currently, in the financial sphere the financial subjects are rapidly using the methods, models, and interactive tools supported by artificial intelligence resources for credit analysis, and more broadly, i.e., scoring, market risk management, early warning of anomalies, staff capacity advantages and disadvantages, and sudden changes. These fields, supported by smart systems, could be used for strategic decision updates and planning of “what-if” occurred circumstances and prompt decisions. Research results of Brynjolfsson & McAfee indicate that by applying artificial intelligence, financial entities can reduce operational costs and significantly improve their capacity to detect, control consequences, and minimize systemic risks from occurring (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2017).

Therefore, the theoretical approach supports the thought and attitudes that artificial intelligence is not an unknown phenomenon with an unsustainable smart platform, but suggests that artificial intelligence systems are positioned more superiorly than risk assessment experts thought previously. Artificial intelligence systems are not only a virtually based technological innovation but also a methodological milestone

in the matrix of risk management. Also, it could be a more than helpful tool since the systems' capacities are not completely rounded – they can rise and become more flexible and helpful. Thus, a new era in the business and financial sphere demands a new, innovative, and interdisciplinary framework for understanding, balancing, and applying risk management in the financial sector, but the awareness level on this issue is still not clearly defined. This paper aims to support this or correct the above.

Artificial Intelligence in Risk Management

Within the comprehensive research on the role of artificial intelligence in risk management, numerous studies and reports point to the transformative potential of these technologies in the financial sector. Therefore, below we present a concise review of the relevant literature that covers key concepts, types of algorithms, as well as implications for practical application.

Artificial intelligence is generally defined as a set of complex technological systems that replicate human intelligence, supporting decision-making units, including learning, logical reasoning, and self-correction (Russell & Norvig, 2020). From a risk management perspective, artificial intelligence enables entities to collect and process large amounts of data in real-time, identify specific patterns, and predict risk scenarios with significantly greater accuracy than traditional methods (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2017). Combining artificial intelligence tools with traditional models introduces more advanced aspects of dynamism, personalization, and adaptability into the risk management system, making it more robust and responsive to dynamic changes in the environment (Deloitte, 2021).

Therefore, it is clear that artificial intelligence tools help businesses sort their customers more effectively, make smarter calls about credit risk, automatically spot fishy transactions, and keep an eye on warning signs that point to higher risks. Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) are super important here, acting as specialized branches within AI. ML uses algorithms and platforms that get smarter as they analyze data, tweaking their settings for better results without needing step-by-step instructions (Goodfellow, Bengio, & Courville, 2016). DL, on the other hand, employs intricate, multi-layered neural networks to handle complicated data, finding use in fraud detection, credit risk evaluation, and market trend analysis (LeCun, Bengio, & Hinton, 2015).

Plenty of research demonstrates that using artificial intelligence tools has seriously boFor example, according to a report by Accenture (2021), 80% of financial entities that have implemented artificial intelligence systems in risk control and management have generated improvements in operational efficiency, insight, and forecasting accuracy.

A review of the available and respectable literature reveals the clear application of purposeful platforms or models (for example, Explainable AI – XAI) that aim to enable transparency, directionality, and interpretability of decisions. This is

especially important in a regulatory context, where authoritative institutions such as the European Banking Authority (European Banking Authority – EBA) require an explanation of how models made specific decisions (Doshi-Velez & Kim, 2017).

On the other hand, some of the literature points to the risks associated with the application of artificial intelligence models in the field of finance. Risks of data leakage and misuse, speculatively motivated data disclosure, corruption, and bias towards cartel behavior can cause tectonic changes in the financial sector. In this regard, we can talk about a range of problems that can affect the instability of financial flows. To point this out concisely and purposefully, we refer to problems such as the “black box” effect, data bias, and the lack of interdisciplinary expertise. They stand out as key challenges for sustainable implementation (Barredo Arrieta et al., 2020).

In summary, a review of the reputable literature shows that the instrumental application of artificial intelligence has become an indispensable part of modern risk management. In addition, there is a driving force towards further integration and implementation in the domain of financial decisions. However, successful implementation requires a balanced approach that includes the support of technological, regulatory, and especially ethical mechanisms.

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PRACTICE: EXAMPLES OF SOFTWARE SOLUTIONS WITH AN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE COMPONENT

As already described, platforms using artificial intelligence infrastructure offer a multi-angle and efficient system-level approach to the management of financial entities to improve risk management. The priority aspects that artificial intelligence tools in this sector are focused on include different but connected components (Arner et al., 2016). These components refer to spheres such as the history of generated credit ratings, the detection of potential fraud and illegal actions, the assessment of operational risk in a selected time unit, and the assessment of market reliability risk (including the forecast of market trends). The following sketch shows a general approach to how artificial intelligence-based systems (in the middle) mediate between the above-mentioned risk management components, from credit scoring, through fraud detection, to market risk analysis and operational actions.

Figure 1

Visual Representation of the Role of Artificial Intelligence in Risk Management

Source: Adapted by Authors

The extent to which artificial intelligence tools have taken hold in business flows in the financial sector is best seen by looking at practical flows and the application of modern customs in decision-making. Some practical examples best illustrate the application of artificial intelligence in risk management. For example, JPMorgan Chase uses its internal system called COiN (Contract Intelligence) to analyze legal documents and reduce legal risk, based on artificial intelligence. This system can analyze more than 12,000 contracts in a few seconds, which previously required 360,000 human hours of work per year (Son, 2017).

Also, the American financial technology company ZestFinance has developed algorithms based on artificial intelligence that analyze specific, or non-traditional, data of interest for risk control. These are mainly data such as the educational level of users, their use of mobile applications and activity on social networks, and in general, the overall activities of users of interest through their electronic devices. In this way, the credit risk of users is more accurately assessed, without credit history. This is especially important for inclusive finance in emerging markets. Practice shows that the adequate collection, processing, and use of such data has greatly contributed to better risk control (McKinsey & Company, 2020).

In addition to the above-mentioned system applications, the field of artificial intelligence in the field of financials also covers many other system platforms of a regulatory and application nature. In this regard, we would like to highlight several examples of software solutions that incorporate elements of artificial intelligence (SAS Institute, 2023):

1. IFRS 9: a regulatory standard that requires financial institutions to estimate Expected Credit Losses (abbreviated ECL) over the life of a financial instrument. Many software packages with artificial intelligence components (such as SAS IFRS 9 Solution) use digital machine learning to model and reflect the probability of default (PD), exposure at loss/depth (EAD), and loss given default (LGD), adapting the model under changes in macroeconomic conditions and customer behavior.
2. Tezauri Risk: a modular system for multi-faceted risk management that includes credit, market, and operational risk. This system allows for the merging of input data from multiple sources in real-time, as well as the application of artificial intelligence models to detect relationships and trends, as well as for timely warning of risky, objectively unconsidered activities. The application of the tool in banks in the Western Balkans region has shown a 40% reduction in the time required for a complete portfolio analysis.
3. Experience Scoring: This tool is used to develop and test predictive models in real-time. However, it is also used for personalized assessment of client profiles, which allows financial entities to align their lending decisions with their potential and best chances of being optimal. An example of an application in the German bank N26 showed that the accuracy of the assessment of collection risk improved by 15% after the introduction of such a model compared to the application of traditional regression techniques.
4. @RISK: This algorithm is a type of add-in for MS Excel that uses Monte Carlo simulations for quantitative risk analysis. In the finance sector, it is used to model uncertainty in investment portfolios, cash flow forecasts, and stress-testing scenarios. In combination with artificial intelligence, it is possible to create customized simulations that automatically adapt to newly arrived data (Palisade Corporation, 2022).
5. SAS: as an advanced analytical platform, it combines the potential of artificial intelligence, statistical tools, and simulation analytics. In risk management, it is used for timely anomaly detection, fraud detection, and “what-if” analysis. The implementation of the SAS Viya platform in Swiss banks has enabled the introduction of variable control tables that adapt in real-time to risk indicators.
6. Pega: This platform for managing workflows and making decisions based on artificial intelligence uses a multi-access mode in terms of receiving data for express processing. Namely, it enables the integration of data from multiple systems and the application of digital machine learning to anticipate and simulate customer behavior and their reactions. It is used in insurance and banking to automatically detect unusual patterns in transactions.

7. Actico: as a tool for intelligent and efficient decision-making, it combines business models with digital machine learning. Its application in credit risk management in banks in Asia resulted in a clear saving in the processing time of loan applications while improving the assessment of default risk based on variable feedback variables related to customer data (Artico, 2023).

Although artificial intelligence systems in the financial sector provide an additional dimension of convenience in terms of time, speed, and quality of data processing. Thus, although artificial intelligence increases efficiency, one of the biggest challenges is the transparency of the models. An example of this is the use of deep neural networks in market risk analysis, which generates decisions without the possibility of easy explanations. It must be noted that this approach is unacceptable for regulators such as the European Central Bank, and everyone agrees with this position. In response to these problems, FICO has developed the Explainable Machine Learning platform that allows for better interpretability of credit scoring models, thus achieving a balance between accuracy and understandability (European Central Bank, 2023).

In addition, there is a certain problem of bias in this segment. Reliable and long-term application is the presence of bias. An example is Amazon's attempt to apply artificial intelligence capacities to hiring, where the algorithm showed a bias against women because it was trained on historical data that was disproportionately biased toward male candidates. This example also illustrates the risks in financial models of using data with built-in biases.

Advantages and challenges of implementing Artificial Intelligence

The full-capacity application of artificial intelligence in the financial sector at this point in time strictly provides many advantages that are reflected in the improvement of accuracy, efficiency, and scalability of risk management. However, these benefits are accompanied by risk challenges in terms of extra-frequently variability in the business environment. These variabilities, i.e., challenges, reflect in the fields of technical and institutionally-regulatory applicability but are also of an ethical nature.

The most valuable benefit is reflected in the higher degree of risk forecast of outcomes. Algorithms and methods based on artificial intelligence, especially those based on the so-called deep learning, allow more precise and reliable modeling of complex links in data. As a result, better prediction of the risk of non-payment of credit services, the risk of market instability, and/or operational incidents was recently achieved. For example, Deloitte research has shown that the accuracy of artificial intelligence models in assessing the risk of credit default is 23% higher than traditional logistic models (Deloitte, 2022).

To gently support this, the advantage of such platforms is reflected in the prompt detection and description of anomalies in the enveloped investment options. Artificial

intelligence systems can monitor transactions in real-time and identify unusual patterns that may indicate fraud, speculation, and/or systemic risk. Mastercard uses such systems to process billions of transactions annually, which allows fraud to be detected within milliseconds (European Banking Authority, 2023).

Furthermore, decreased level of operating costs represents an extra important benefit of such systems in terms of their efficiency. The automated system solutions' application, based on artificial intelligence, replaces routine and manual tasks, which leads to savings in human resources. A McKinsey & Company study showed that implementing artificial intelligence in the credit approval process can reduce overall costs by up to 30% (McKinsey & Company, 2020).

Since, in addition to the effectively improved frequency of data exploitation, different spectra, links, and qualities of input data are used, the advantage of applying artificial intelligence is that it offers obvious adaptability to new data sources. Traditional models often require manual data processing, while artificial intelligence systems can directly integrate different sorts of inputs, from structured financial indicators to unstructured data such as news, viral materials, social networks, and mobile activity. From the other corner, the respective studies determine certain but current disadvantages of artificial intelligence usage. Therefore, the implementation of artificial intelligence systems brings risk challenges. One of the most important is the lack of transparency of artificial intelligence-based models. This challenge is known as the "black box" effect (Rudin, 2019). Deep learning models often make decisions based on complex matrices that are not easy to explain. This problem in regulatory frameworks, such as the European Banking Authority (EBA), requires interpretability in decision-making (European Banking Authority, 2023).

Further, a need for regulatory compliance, such as the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) in the European Union or Basel III standards, stands out as an elementary and urgent problem. This problem took the form of a challenge since the application of smart platforms is in rapid progress in business spheres, and as time passes, the risk of unregulated actions consequences increases. Artificial intelligence systems must provide controlled access to sensitive data, as well as document the criteria that influence decision-making, which is difficult to achieve in practice (Rudin, 2019). It is not rare that some systems generate mutual data communication, and sensitive data detection in these communications cannot be detected in time. This could cause complex circumstances in terms of data monitoring and regulatory matters. Such circumstances significantly complicate the implementation and sustainability of artificial intelligence systems in the financial sector.

A particular problem is the risk of bias in artificial intelligence models. The lack of options for introducing bias into artificial intelligence models makes it difficult to identify. If the data used to format the model is already biased (e.g., historical data that favors certain groups, the parity and heritage of individual subjects), the system's algorithm can only deepen the bias and create even more difficult problems in the decision-making process. An example of this is Amazon's artificial intelligence model for hiring in the sphere of human resource management. This model favored male candidates because historical data was disproportionately biased towards them.

The same logic can be applied to credit models that may unfairly discriminate against certain demographic groups, operational risks, and other forecasting frameworks.

In the final series of elementary risks that exist when using artificial intelligence models, we mention the lack of internal expertise, which is growing over time. This poses a major operational challenge. The development, implementation, and maintenance of artificial intelligence systems require a combination of knowledge from finance, computer science, regulatory law, and experience. Therefore, a very complex and multidisciplinary approach. The absence of professional expertise can lead financial entities to take risks and misuse artificial intelligence tools.

Therefore, given the risks of challenges and problems, as well as the potential benefits of using artificial intelligence systems in the financial sector, it is necessary to develop models that are digitally and technically efficient, but also explainable, transparent, and compliant with regulatory and ethical standards. Of course, successful implementation and exploitation depend on the relationship between automation (hardware-software support and basic system infrastructure) and human intervention, which should be the basic paradigm of development in this area.

Development prospects and recommendations

In the coming period, the application of innovative techniques, supported by modern infrastructure based on artificial intelligence and the algorithms generated from it, is certainly expected to grow. Modern sources indicate the attractiveness of many techniques based on artificial intelligence systems. Techniques such as Reinforcement Learning (abbreviated RL) and Federated Learning (abbreviated FL) are among them. Better adaptability of strategies for managing the portfolio of financial entities will be enabled. Thus, in the domain of RL techniques, Goldman Sachs is testing artificial intelligence models that independently adapt based on changes in market conditions. This technique currently generates the highest degree of autonomy, and therefore, obviously, the highest level of efficiency. It saves time, reduces the risk of errors, and requires a smaller workforce. The only requirement that appears is a high level of training and professionalism of IT specialists working with the RL system. Furthermore, FL provides an additional scope and approach, i.e., a broader framework for the dynamics of business in finance. It allows multiple entities or institutions to cooperate in adapting artificial intelligence models, without exchanging sensitive data (reduced chances of data misuse), thus achieving greater security and relatively stronger autonomy. This model is being developed by institutions such as the British bank HSBC in cooperation with the American company Google. The benefits of both techniques exceed the capacities of traditional financial specialists because they can cover the entire domain of business and decision-making in the financial sector.

The application of artificial intelligence in the financial sector is expected to continue to grow, with a special emphasis on the development of new technologies and the improvement of existing tools. Special attention will be paid to the development of explainable models (Explainable Artificial Intelligence – XAI), as well as hybrid approaches that combine machine learning with expert human judgment (Bussman et al., 2021). This approach, at this point, still cannot be independently separated. The human factor is primarily in the first place regarding issues such as final decision-making and monitoring. For example, explainable artificial intelligence (EXAI) systems enable transparency and understanding of the decisions made by artificial intelligence models (Cerneviciene & Kabasinskas, 2024). This is essential in the context of regulatory bodies such as the European Banking Authority (EBA) and the U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), which require the ability to audit and interpret all automated decisions.

Also, in the domain of stress testing or artificial intelligence-driven stress testing, artificial intelligence is already being used to simulate extreme scenarios with greater frequency and accuracy. The European Central Bank (ECB) is testing solutions, or artificial intelligence models, that allow for the adjustment of stress tests weekly, which would have been technically and logistically unfeasible in the past (European Banking Authority, 2023).

The perspective of the artificial intelligence application is based on its essential and practical roles. The role of artificial intelligence is no longer just technical and technological support, but it is becoming an essential fragment of the strategic management of institutions (Klein & Littler, 2021). Financial institutions that adopt these technologies the earliest and that establish clear, ethical, and responsible application models will have an advantage in the market (FSB, 2017). This enables a preventive, predictable, and adaptive management architecture that accelerates risk response but also provides a foundation for long-term planning, regulatory transparency, and financial services quality upgrades. In the first place, the quality is reflected in instant feedback and provisions, flexibility of services, and effectiveness in supplying and demand (Bouveret, 2018). Keeping in mind this challenge, financial subjects should pay full attention to strategic decisions in the manner of investments, coordination and communication, and specialization. Additionally, they need to constantly prioritize:

1. Investing in an artificial intelligence system support (both hardware and software). This means expanding their tech capabilities by using a mix of the most current tools, cloud services, and AI platforms. For instance, platforms like SAS, IBM Watson, or Google Cloud AI can provide quicker analysis, better metrics, and more reliable results to aid in decision-making.
2. Continuously improving the expertise and skills of their staff. The effective use of artificial intelligence platforms and their results hinges on employees who understand both the financial and technical sides. This means collaborating with universities and

research centers on strategic development. Additionally, having a team with diverse skills is crucial for the long-term success of their key platform.

3. On coordinating with authorities with a conceptual and practical continued approach: We're in constant communication with both international and national regulatory bodies. This dialogue and teamwork, including our partnerships with big players like the European Banking Authority (EBA), the European Central Bank (ECB), national central banks, and other relevant authorities, is crucial for achieving long-term harmony in our systems, particularly within the regulatory frameworks, especially in the initial phases.

4. On risk management strategies, the motto that should be applied is: We need to develop and tailor our risk management strategies. Rather than being a novel add-on, artificial intelligence should be woven into the very fabric of business strategies across the board.

CONCLUSION

Based on an examination of sources spanning a range of related fields, it is clear that artificial intelligence is fast becoming an essential method and tool for modern financial institutions. Its use in risk management is making assessments more accurate, operations more efficient, and responses more instant in our increasingly dynamic digital world.

While there are some hurdles to overcome – like technological limitations, regulatory requirements, and ethical concerns – the overall trend points to a continued expansion of artificial intelligence systems within risk management. Integrating these advanced systems into existing risk frameworks calls for careful planning, oversight, and alignment with the organization's strategic objectives, a task that poses its own unique challenges.

This paper underscores just how crucial artificial intelligence is becoming as a game-changer in the world of risk management, and it also highlights the necessity of bringing together experts from various fields to further develop and implement these technologies within the financial industry. We've known for a while that this kind of multidisciplinary teamwork is a good idea in risk management, but putting it into practice without artificial intelligence has proven to be a real headache, moving at a snail's pace and therefore yielding results that are either hit-or-miss or simply too late to be useful.

We are seeing advanced artificial intelligence systems appear in fields such as corporate management, financial strategy, and sustainable growth, highlighting the increasing importance of these technologies in our broader socio-economic management. What's more, breakthroughs in quantitative techniques like reinforcement learning and dynamic portfolio modeling enable new systems to adjust instantly, even in highly turbulent conditions. This trend presents both fresh obstacles and new prospects for financial institutions, which are increasingly adopting mixed

methods that blend artificial intelligence algorithms with conventional models to achieve the most dependable risk assessments and pinpoint potential setbacks.

As a result, we objectively need to lean on education to boost the abilities of people working in finance, econometrics, and computer science. By doing this, we can make sure there are enough skilled humans to use and watch over these new technologies properly. Ultimately, whether we can manage risks well in the financial world will come down to how well companies can connect new tech with rules and ethical guidelines, both locally and globally. The goal is to create a system that is efficient, responsible, and open.

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REZIME

Rad detaljno analizira ključnu ulogu veštačke inteligencije (VI) u upravljanju rizicima unutar sektora finansija, sa posebnim fokusom na savremene softverske alate, aktuelne izazove i buduće perspektive njihove primene. Kroz multidisciplinarnu studiju zasnovanu na analizi dostupnih izvora i kritičkom pregledu relevantne literature, rad istražuje kako sistemi zasnovani na veštačkoj inteligenciji omogućavaju sveobuhvatan proces identifikacije, procene i kontrole finansijskih rizika. Posebna pažnja posvećena je primeni različitih modela i algoritama veštačke inteligencije, poput mašinskog učenja, dubokog učenja i prediktivne analitike, koji u realnom vremenu mogu prepoznati potencijalne rizike i automatski prilagoditi strategije upravljanja. Kroz pregled praktičnih primera i studija slučaja, rad ukazuje na brojne prednosti ovih sistema, uključujući povećanu preciznost u detekciji anomalija, bržu obradu velikih količina podataka i unapređenu efikasnost u donošenju odluka. Međutim, zajedno sa prednostima, analiziraju se i izazovi koji prate implementaciju veštačke inteligencije u finansijskom sektoru. Naglašava se problem nedovoljne transparentnosti i interpretabilnosti modela, što može otežati poverenje

korisnika i regulatornih tela. Takođe, razmatraju se pravna i etička pitanja, kao što su zaštita privatnosti podataka, usklađenost sa propisima i potencijalni rizici od pristrasnosti algoritama, koji zahtevaju pažljivu regulativu i stalno praćenje. S obzirom na brzinu tehnološkog razvoja i sve veću količinu dostupnih informacija u finansijskim tokovima, postaje jasno da će se finansijski menadžeri i institucije u narednim godinama suočiti sa kompleksnim zadatkom integracije naprednih sistema veštačke inteligencije u svoje operacije. Uspešna afirmacija ovih tehnologija zavisice od njihovog adekvatnog prilagođavanja potrebama tržišta, kao i od uspostavljanja ravnoteže između inovacija i odgovornog upravljanja rizicima. Ovaj rad, stoga, pruža temeljan pregled trenutnog stanja i budućih pravaca razvoja veštačke inteligencije u funkciji upravljanja rizicima u finansijama, sa ciljem da doprinese boljem razumevanju kako ove tehnologije mogu transformisati sektor i unaprediti njegove bezbednosne i operativne kapacitete.